

Implementation of lean production practices and manufacturing performance: The role of lean duration

Wickramasinghe, G.L.D

Department of Textile and Clothing Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Wickramasinghe, V.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

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Implementation of lean production practices and manufacturing performance – the role of lean duration

Abstract

Purpose- The purpose of the research is to investigate the effects of lean production practices and lean duration (the duration for which lean production is in operation) on manufacturing performance.

Design/methodology/approach- The survey was used as the main method of data collection. In addition to survey data collected from 1189 respondents from export-based textile and apparel firms operating in Sri Lanka, longitudinal data were collected over a period of seven months from a firm in the study sample to corroborate the survey findings.

Findings- The findings revealed that lean production practices significantly enhance manufacturing performance. Further findings revealed the importance of the duration of lean production in operation in achieving higher levels of manufacturing performance. This provides empirical support for the contention that the adoption of lean production can only be achieved through time.

Practical implications- Findings have implications for practices of export-based textile and apparel producing countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa, which are competing intensively with each other for their market share in the global export-based textile and apparel production.

Originality/value- Manufacturing firms are adopting production methods and management practices to become leaner and fitter to create a new labour intensive production model that generate distinctive internal capabilities for survival and growth in international markets. Academics and practitioners in the field of manufacturing technologies will be interested in better understanding how lean production practices would enhance manufacturing performance from a non-Western developing country context.

Key words Lean production; lean production practices; manufacturing performance; Sri Lanka

Paper type Research paper

Introduction

Advanced manufacturing approaches play a major role in organisations' responses to global competition. One of the most popular advanced manufacturing approaches is lean production (Doolen and Hacker, 2005; Vinodh et al., 2011). Organizations belonging to different business sectors throughout the world have implemented lean production concept in pursuit of increased organizational performance (Bhasin and Burcher, 2006; Chay et al., 2015; Narayanamurthy and Gurumurthy, 2016; Panwar et al., 2015; Taj and Morosan, 2011). The literature provides evidence that successful implementation of lean production practices creates a streamlined, high quality system that produces products and services with increased productivity, reduced cost, shortened lead times and increased volume flexibility, which ultimately enhances organisations' performance (Shah and Ward, 2003). However, some previous studies (such as Doolen and Hacker, 2005) provide evidence that many of the organizations that implemented lean production have experienced limited success in achieving increased organizational outcomes, such as increased competitiveness. Therefore, it is possible to question the actual competitive impact of lean production. In this context, the objective of this research was to investigate the effects of lean production practices on manufacturing performance. In doing so, we further investigated the effect of lean duration (the duration for which lean production is in operation) on manufacturing performance.

The present study is conducted in the export-based textile and apparel production industry in Sri Lanka. The export-based textile and apparel production is one of the leading manufacturing industries in Sri Lanka, which has emerged as the country's main export earner and the largest single employment provider in the industrial sector (Lopez-Acevedo and Robertson, 2016). Owing to rising wages in the labour intensive global export-based textile and apparel industry, production operations shifted from Hong Kong, South Korea, and Taiwan, who were the leaders in the export-based textile and apparel production by the late 1970s, to Sri Lanka, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, China, India, and Pakistan. Thereafter, it has, further shifted to other countries with relatively lower labour cost in Asia (such as Laos, Cambodia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam), Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa. Today, export-based textile and apparel producing countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa compete intensively with each other for their market share in the global export-based textile and apparel production (for further details Lopez-Acevedo and Robertson, 2016). Since the mid-2000s, in response to increasing labour costs in Sri Lanka,

export-based textile and apparel manufacturers in Sri Lanka identified possibilities for them to turn to lean production for improving the efficiency of production systems (Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2016, 2012). The attributes of lean production (refer to Womack and Jones, 1996), such as integrated, single piece production flow, low inventory, and close integration from raw material to customer through partnership fit with the high-volume repetitive labour intensive export-based textile and apparel production environment in Sri Lanka. As a result, firms are changing their production methods and management practices to become leaner and fitter to create a new labour intensive production model that generate distinctive internal capabilities for survival and growth in international markets.

The novelty of the current study lies in the following aspects. First, we used a rigorous methodology to uncover lean production practices. In doing so, we collected information from firms where practices have already been implemented, in contrast to firms where implementation is intended, firms where implementation failed, and firms where practices were poorly had implemented. Second, we evaluated manufacturing performance of textile and apparel manufacturing plants. Therefore, it is expected that this research will provide valuable information for academics, managers and policy makers to make informed decisions on the operation of textile and apparel manufacturing plants. Third, although Womack and Jones (1996) state that lean manufacturing can only be achieved through time, and lean production could not be used as a panacea to solve short-term competitive problems, it is very rare to find empirical studies that investigated the effects of lean duration. Therefore, it is expected that this research will guide future research by developing propositions and suggesting a research agenda for further inquiry and understanding.

Consistent with the objectives, the next section reviews, in brief, the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry.

Review of literature

Lean production

Lean production centres on the elimination of waste and creation of value (Womack and Jones, 1996). Waste in the context of lean production includes all that does not add value to the product or service from the customer's perspective. Hence, waste is diverse including overproduction, waiting times, unnecessary movement of materials, inappropriate processing, inventory, defects, underutilization of people, environmental waste, and underutilization of

facilities. Value added activities include activities perceived as being important by the customer and those are performed correctly the first time (Vinodh et al., 2011; Womack and Jones, 1996).

Womack et al. (1990, p. 13) provided a comprehensive definition of lean production covering both efficiency and effectiveness attributes of manufacturing performance. According to them “lean production ... is lean because it uses less of everything compared to mass production - half the human effort in factory, half the manufacturing space, half the investment in tools, half the engineering hours to develop a new product in half time. Also, it requires keeping far less than half the needed inventory on site, results in fewer defects, and produces a greater and ever growing variety of products”. This definition addresses efficiency of the system by incorporating the relationship between input and output while effectiveness of the system by incorporating the relationship between output and the organization’s goals. Shah and Ward (2007, p. 791) defined lean production as “an integrated socio-technical system whose main objective is to eliminate waste by concurrently reducing or minimizing supplier, customer, and internal variability”.

According to Womack and Jones (1996) five critical elements of lean implementation are value, value stream, flow, pull, and the pursuit of perfection. Specifying of value allows to understand customer needs. Value stream analysis allows to distinguish between activities that are required to deliver a product to the customer and non-value added activities. Flow implies that products and services should progress steadily and smoothly through all the value-creating steps in the value stream without stops, delays, interruptions, defects, etc. (Womack and Jones, 1996). Pull suggests that firms should produce goods or services when the customer asks for it while perfection is used to suggest the need of continuous improvement (Womack and Jones, 1996).

Lean production practices

Lean production practices are the practices implemented and the changes made to eliminate waste and create value (Dal Pont et al., 2008; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1999; Shah and Ward, 2003). The literature suggests organizations should introduce a bundle of multifaceted lean production practices that work synergistically to minimize waste and thereby successfully implement a lean production system (Bortolotti et al, 2015; Furlan et al., 2011; Flynn et al., 1999; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996; Shah and Ward, 2003). This multifaceted bundle of lean production practices are also referred to as determinants of a lean production system (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996).

At the very detailed level, these lean production practices include but not limited to practices such as cellular manufacturing, multifunctional workforce, lot size reduction, Just-in-time (JIT), work delegation, total productive maintenance (TPM), set-up time reduction, total quality management (TQM), continuous flow production, agile manufacturing strategies, safety improvement programmes, process capability measurements, and human resource management (HRM) (Flynn et al. 1999; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996; Shah and Ward, 2003 and 2007). The majority of previous studies reduced a lengthy list of lean production practices by classifying them into broad categories using data reduction techniques (e.g. Furlan et al., 2011; Panizzolo, 1998; Shah and Ward, 2003 and 2007). After an extensive review of literature, Table 1 was created to provide a representative view of such broadly classified lean production practices. It is apparent from Table 1 that there is no consensus on the number of lean production practices that should be bundled. For instance, Koufteros et al., (1998) identified seven broad practices that lead to time compression in time-based manufacturing. Flynn et al. (1999) identified 10 main practices that lead to world class manufacturing.

Further, as can be seen in Table 1, the studies by Shah and Ward (2003), Doolen and Hacker (2005), Karlsson and Åhlström (1999), and Panizzolo (1998) become prominent since these attempted to propose broad classifications for lean production practices. Shah and Ward (2003) broadly classified the lean production practices into four, namely, JIT (included practices such as lot size reductions, pull system, and cycle time reductions), TQM (included practices such as quality management programs, process capability measurements, and formal continuous improvement programme), TPM (included practices such as predictive or preventive maintenance, safety improvement programs, and planning and scheduling strategies) and HRM (included self-directed work teams and flexible, cross-functional workforce). Karlsson and Åhlström (1999) identified nine lean production practices as elimination of waste, continuous improvement, zero defects, JIT deliveries, pull of materials, multifunctional teams, decentralisation, integration of functions, and vertical information systems.

Table 1

Some researchers such as Hayes and Wheelwright (1984) and Sakakibara et al. (1997) reduced categorisations by further simplifying them. Hayes and Wheelwright (1984)

classified lean production practices into two broad categories of structural and infrastructural factors, where structural categories included capacity, facilities, technology, and vertical integration while infrastructural categories included workforce, quality, production planning/materials, and organization. Sakakibara et al. (1997) classified lean production practices into two broad categories of infrastructure practices and JIT practices, where infrastructure practices included quality management, workforce management, manufacturing strategy, organizational characteristics, product design while JIT practices included set-up time reduction, schedule flexibility, maintenance, equipment layout, Kanban and JIT supplier relationships.

A term used in conjunction with lean production is *leanness*, which is the relative measure of how lean the system is or the extent of adoption of lean production practices (Bayou and de Korvin, 2008; Bhasin, 2011; Wan and Chen, 2008). For instance, Comm and Mathaisel (2000) described leanness as a relative measure for whether a firm is lean or not. Naylor et al. (1999) defined leanness as developing a value stream to eliminate all types of waste to ensure a *level* schedule. Wan and Chen (2008) used the term leanness to refer to the performance level of a value stream compared to perfection, which shows how lean the system is. According to Bayou and de Korvin (2008), a firm can achieve different levels of leanness, namely, lean to leaner to leanest by improving its efficiency, effectiveness or both; the leanest level is the state of perfection.

It is important to assess leanness or the extent of adoption lean production practices since such an assessment allows to evaluate how lean the system is (Bayou and de Korvin, 2008; Bhasin, 2011; Wan and Chen, 2008). In our study we used the term leanness to describe the degree of adoption of lean production practices. Our review of literature suggests that broadly classified lean production practices shown in Table 1 could be used to determine leanness of the system or the extent of adoption of lean production.

Effect of lean production practices on manufacturing performance

Manufacturing performance is explained in terms of various dimensions such as manufacturing plant's labour efficiency (Arthur, 1994), machine efficiency (Youndt et al., 1996), conformance quality (Cua et al., 2001; Swink et al., 2007), manufacturing plant productivity (Ichniowski et al., 1997), schedule attainment (Bozarth et al., 2009), on-time delivery (Sakakibara et al., 1997; Swink et al., 2007; Youndt et al., 1996), inventory management (Hofer et al., 2012; Youndt et al., 1996), production volume flexibility (Cua et al., 2001; Swink et al., 2007) and manufacturing cost efficiency (Bozarth et al., 2009; Swink

et al., 2007). Overall, the achievements in manufacturing performance enhance a firm's manufacturing competitive capabilities (Jabbour et al., 2013; Swink et al., 2007).

The operations management literature identifies that the simultaneous implementation of a bundle of lean production practices may result in positive operational performance outcomes or lean performance outcomes by streamlining processes and increasing process consistency (Birdi et al., 2008; Shah and Ward, 2003). The underline principle is that although lean production practices are diverse, these are complementary and inter-related to each other (Birdi et al., 2008; Flynn et al., 1995; Furlan et al., 2011; Sakakibara et al., 1997; Shah and Ward, 2003). For example, Flynn et al. (1995, p. 1354) concluded that although JIT and TQM have positive effects on performance in isolation, their combination yields synergies that lead to further performance improvements. Shah and Ward (2003, p. 146) concluded that their findings provide unambiguous evidence for the synergistic effect of lean production practices on better manufacturing performance suggesting that lean production practices should coexist. Further, the studies of Cua et al. (2001) and Shah and Ward (2003) provided evidence for significant positive effects of lean production practices on operational performance. Therefore, it is hypothesized for the study:

- H1. Simultaneous implementation of a bundle of lean production practices results in positive manufacturing plant outcomes.

Lean duration

Womack and Jones (1996) state that lean manufacturing can only be achieved through time, and lean manufacturing should not be used as a panacea to solve short-term competitive problems. Further, the operations management literature provides empirical evidence that variations could be found in different dimensions based on how long the lean production is in operation (Birdi et al., 2008; Sohal and Egglestone 1994). For instance, when investigating the extent to which lean production has been implemented and what are the structural changes taking place as a result of the implementation in Australian organizations, Sohal and Egglestone (1994) highlighted the importance of collecting data on how long the lean production system is in operation at each firm. In this context, we propose that when investigating the adoption of lean production practices, lean duration is an important variable. The longer the lean production practices have been implemented, the greater will be the improved outcomes resulting from lean implementation. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H2. Lean duration moderates the relationship between adoption of lean production practices and lean performance outcomes in such a way that the longer the lean duration the greater will be lean performance outcomes.

Methodology

Population and sample

The data collection was restricted to firms belonging to Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) 22 and 23 (22 -Textile mill products, 23 - Apparel and other finished products made from fabrics and similar materials). The following criteria were set in selecting the firms belonging to the study population: 1) a firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) since it is compulsory that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 per cent of their output, 2) a firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing plant and it should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This restriction isolates firms that had achieved good progress in lean statistics such as work in progress (WIP), first time through (FTT), efficiency of the process, delivery in full on time, accepted quality level (AQL) and cut ship, and 3) firms with more than 100 employees were selected. We identified 14 firms that fulfilled the above mentioned criteria. With regard to the characteristics of these firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1993 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2004. The ownership of all the firms lay with locals. All the firms have adopted lean production methods after 2005, where the latest adoption occurred in two of the firms in the year 2010. On average, these firms have achieved good progress in the implementation of lean with WIP (days) of 35, FTT (%) of 70, efficiency of the process (%) of 90, deliver in full on time (DIFOT) (%) of 85, AQL (%) of 91, and cut ship (%) of 90. All the firms had a dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior level manager.

When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an average annual turnover (in US\$) ranging from 80 to 400 Million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5000. After the implementation of lean production systems many of the lower level job positions were enriched with decision making authority. Therefore, job positions above supervisory grades are considered as managerial level in the firms. Approximately 30% of the workforce can be identified as managerial job positions. Some of the managerial level job positions created as a result of lean implementation can be identified as team leaders, quality leaders, line supervisors, finishing supervisors, merchandising officers, work-study officers, industrial

engineering executives, fabric technologists, garment technologist, fashion design and pattern makers and quality assurance executives. These are in addition to conventional middle and senior level managerial positions of the organizational hierarchy. In terms of the level of education of the workforce, middle and senior level managerial employees had bachelor's degrees as the highest level of education. Lower level managerial position holders had diploma or certificate level qualifications, or 13 years of full-time secondary education leading to General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level). According to Lopez-Acevedo and Robertson (2016, p. 12), Sri Lankan employees in this industry are ranked as the highest educated among global export-apparel production countries. For the main survey, employees in the job positions of supervisor or above were randomly selected from the above mentioned 14 firms. Survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 20% of the supervisor or above level employees in each firm, and not more than 10% of employees were selected from the same department/unit. Total of 1189 responses were received.

Main study - measures

The independent variables of the study are lean production practices. The operations management literature emphasises the need of distinguishing intended practices from implemented practices (Shah and Ward, 2007). In our study, we took into account lean production practices that had been already implemented in the production floor (and become standard of practices for at least one year – also refer to sample selection criteria). In identifying appropriate lean production practices we adopted three mechanisms. First, we identified practices that contributed to the implementation of lean production systems from prior theoretical and empirical work (refer to Table 1). Second, we did a preliminary investigation to identify mostly implemented lean production practices to facilitate the lean implementation on our study population (= sample). We obviously included those lean production practices about which we could collect data. Third, we tried to figure out practices that were not prominent in the literature and not highly identified as implemented by the firms, but appeared to fit into the study. Based on the above procedure we developed a scale of 38 items. In finalizing these scale items, we consulted a panel of academics and practitioners to assess face and content validity of the scale items. We operationalized lean production practices as the extent to which these had been implemented as experienced by supervisor or above level employees attached to production function. Responses were obtained on a 5-point Likert-scale scored from 1 'strongly disagree' to 5 'strongly agree' to measure the leanness or the extent of adoption of lean production practices. Higher scores are

therefore indicative of greater experience. To ensure face and content validity of the scale items we pre-tested the scale items with a sample of supervisor or above level employees attached to production function.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were performed on the variables to identify and confirm underline factor structures associated with lean production practices. We followed recommended procedure and guidelines of Hair et al. (2006). Accordingly, we tested EFA using SPSS for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias; convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7; AVE values should be above 0.5; the square root of AVE for a given construct should be greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs (refer to Hair et al., 2006). The scale had Cronbach's alpha of 0.716 suggesting good internal consistency reliability; total variation explained was 69.35. As can be seen from Table 2, fit indices revealed good factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability. To confirm the factor structures yielded for lean production practices from SPSS, we conducted CFA using AMOS following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) recommendation. Accordingly, we assessed CFA results based on chi-square and fit indices. With regard to fit indices, comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) were used. We conducted a series of CFA for the 38-item lean production practices scale and indices yielded for χ^2/df statistic and CFI, TLI and RMSEA confirmed that the factors yielded from SPSS as the best fitting with $\chi^2/df = 3.373$, CFI = .966, TLI = .930, and RMSEA = .012. These 38 practices and 7 broadly classified practices are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

With regard to manufacturing performance (dependent variable), we operationalized the term “manufacturing performance” to mean performance indicators that are directly

affected due to the adoption of lean production. We used the same three mechanisms mentioned under lean production practices to identify most commonly used operational performance measures by our study population. Based on the above procedure we developed a scale of 7 items. These seven items are shown in Table 4. Responses were obtained on a 5-point Likert-scale scored from 1 ‘strongly disagree’ to 5 ‘strongly agree’ to measure the extent of operational performance. Higher scores are therefore indicative of greater performance. We used the same procedure mentioned above to ensure the face and content validity of the items.

We used above mentioned procedure to identify and confirm underline factor structure associated with manufacturing performance. The scale had Cronbach’s alpha of 0.790 suggesting good internal consistency reliability; total variation explained was 61.51. As can be seen from Table 3, fit indices revealed good factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability. We conducted a series of CFA for the 7-item manufacturing performance scale and indices yielded for χ^2/df statistic and CFI, TLI and RMSEA confirmed that the factors yielded from SPSS as the best fitting with $\chi^2/df = 3.855$, CFI = .974, TLI = .864, and RMSEA = .037. As shown in Table 3, all the seven practices were loaded into a single factor. We also collected data on *lean duration* or the duration of lean production in operation in years (moderator variable).

Table 3

Wilks’ Lambda statistic was obtained to check whether any group differences exist among the responses from the 14 firms for the variables of the study. The results of the Wilks’ Lambda statistics for the variables revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) among the responses from the 14 firms. The literature recommends that when the predictor and moderator variables are measured on a continuous scale, the hierarchical regression procedure that retains the continuous nature of the variables is preferred over using cut points (Aiken and West, 1991). Therefore, hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to test the moderation effect. The variables were entered into the regression equation in three steps. The independent variable was added in the first step, the moderator variable was added in the second step, and the interaction term was added in the third step (Fraizer et al., 2004). The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium, and high scores of the variables. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to

determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (CI).

Data from a single firm over seven months' period

One of the firms included in the 14 firms that we have studied agreed to provide data on lean production practices and manufacturing performance over a period of seven (7) months. With regard to lean production practices, the same survey items mentioned above were used at the end of each month to assess the extent of adoption lean production practices (independent variable). Total responses from this firm were 104 (n=104). As shown in Figure 3, we plotted these data for the seven months. The firm provided actual data on five areas of manufacturing performance, namely, AQL (in %), cut ship (in %), DIFOT (in %), raw material on time delivery (in %) and dock to dock (in days) (dependent variables). In this case study, the firm provided one data point per month for seven (7) months for each of the five measures (i.e., AQL values for each month of July to January, as shown in Figure 4). As can be seen from Table 3, in the main survey mentioned above we used these areas as subjective measures to measure our dependent variable “manufacturing performance”. However, we only used the data of this case study to corroborate the survey findings of the effect of lean duration on manufacturing performance.

Results and discussion

Survey results

The means, standard deviations, and zero-order correlations for the study variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 4

We performed moderation analyses based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% CI for the size and significance of the effects. The results for the moderator effect of lean duration on manufacturing performance are shown in Table 5. As shown in Table 5(model 1), all the lean production practices significantly positively relate to manufacturing performance. This supports H1. As shown in Table 5 (model 2), lean duration significantly impacts on manufacturing performance ($p < 0.001$). As indicated by the

significant interaction term in Table 5 (model 3), lean duration moderates the relationships between each lean production practice and manufacturing performance. Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrate the interaction effects for each lean production practice and lean duration on manufacturing performance. The interaction effects for each lean production practice and lean duration on manufacturing performance are significant at the 95% level of significance, as indicated when the lower and upper levels of the confidence intervals did not include zero. This supports H2.

Table 5

Figure 1

Figure 2

Data from a single firm over seven months' period

Figure 3 was created based on data obtained on lean production practices over a period of seven (7) months. Accordingly, it is clear that the extent of adoption of lean production practices getting greater with the increase in lean duration over 7 months' period. This supports our survey findings that lean duration is an important factor in lean production.

Figure 3

Figure 4 were created based on data provided on manufacturing performance over a period of seven (7) months. As can be seen in Figure 4, percentages of cut ship, DIFOT, AQL and raw material on time delivery were increased with the increase in lean duration over seven months' period. This supports our survey findings that lean duration is an important factor in lean production.

Figure 4

Conclusion and implications

We empirically investigated the relationships between lean production practices, lean duration or the duration for which lean production is in operation and manufacturing performance of textile and apparel production. The data were collected from the main survey of firms that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study. The analysis led to identify waste minimization, defects minimization, cross-functional teams, continuous improvement, JIT and pull, information availability and employee involvement as a bundle of lean production practices. The findings of the study supported the hypothesis (H1), which predicted that the simultaneous implementation of these seven lean production practices results in positive manufacturing plant outcomes. The analysis of moderator effect of lean duration supported the hypothesis (H2), which predicted that lean duration moderates the relationship between the adoption of lean production practices and lean performance outcomes in such a way that the longer the lean duration the greater will be lean performance outcomes. To corroborate the results of the main survey, we collected longitudinal data over a period of seven months from a firm in the study sample. Since it is very rare to find prior empirical studies that integrated all these variables in the context of textile and apparel production, we believe that the findings of our study make unique contributions to the literature, and have implications for both theory and practice.

With regard to the implications of the findings for the literature, first, we empirically investigated a bundle of diverse and inter-related lean production practices. In doing so, we empirically investigated implemented lean production practices in contrast to intended practices. Therefore, our operational measures of lean production practices reflect the operational landscape of the firms. The results suggested that lean production practices can be represented with seven factors. Each of these seven practices is important in assessing the degree of adoption of lean production. At the same time, inter-correlations between these seven factors suggest interconnections among these practices and their collective importance. Further, we provided evidence for a significant positive relationship between lean production practices and manufacturing performance. Therefore, our results make unique contributions to the literature, and also from non-Western context. As such, the findings will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Second, the findings revealed the importance of the duration of lean production in operation in achieving higher levels of manufacturing performance. Hence, our empirical findings support Womack and Jones (1996) that the adoption of lean production can only be achieved through time. Hence, we could argue that if a firm exploited (develop, institute, and

implement) each of these lean production practices to its highest potential, over time (with the increase in the duration of lean production in operation) it may be able to create a lean production system that could yield the highest performance through incremental improvement. Although globalisation leads to move ideas all over the world generating a set of standardised practices and policies, this finding implies that early implementers may have more advantages than followers. We identify this as one of the unique contributions of our study since our extensive review of literature led to reveal the difficulty of finding the experiences of introduction of new manufacturing systems in emerging or developing countries in textile and apparel production. Therefore, the findings will be valuable to other export-based textile and apparel producing countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa, which are competing intensively with each other for their market share in the global export-based textile and apparel production.

Third, one of the firms in our sample provided access to actual data on manufacturing performance over a period of seven months, which allowed us to collect data on the adoption of lean production practices covering the same period. Hence, we had the opportunity to corroborate our survey findings with more confidence. We have not seen any previous studies providing such longitudinal data in the literature.

With regard to the managerial implications of the findings for practice, first, we showed using empirical survey data and secondary data from the case study firm the importance of lean duration in lean implementations. This is vital when firms operate in almost similar environmental conditions. Our study was on the lean production practices adopted by export-based firms. On the one hand, when firms face with similar environmental conditions (i.e., political, legal, economic, social and also export market) they may orient towards mimicking best practices that other firms had adopted. On the other hand, a firm could enjoy competitive advantage by adopting distinctive practices, which are the basis of inimitability (Barney and Wright, 1998). Then the question arises, how could firms compete more effectively by adopting similar sets of lean production practices in the view of rapid globalisation? Here, the duration of lean implementation becomes critical. A firm could develop practice flexibility (of lean production practices) overtime to respond quickly to a variety of environmental changes by re-synthesising, re-configuring, and re-deploying its practices. Therefore, the lean duration creates a situation where a bundle of lean production practices are much more difficult to be imitated compared to individual practices since imitation demands an understanding of precise mechanisms by which each element interacts.

Second, Sri Lanka, like other Asian countries, moving towards operating in a global market offering a liberal and dynamic business environment; this is expected to bring economic, social and strategic benefits for the country. Government led development initiatives through foreign direct investment and domestic investment led to create new business sectors in the country. Changes occurred with the globalization of business operations and increase in operating costs in the West increased the importance of developing countries in the manufacturing and export trade. The export-based sector presented in this paper relies on people for the success. Being labour intensive industries, arrangements made by the firms to implement lean production could provide valuable information to academics and practitioners

Third, as we have detailed in the section on *Sample* of our main survey, our study population (= sample) consisted of 14 firms and we yielded 1189 responses from these firms. The data analysis had not revealed any significant differences among the firms on our study variables. Therefore, the results can be generalizable. However, future studies are needed from a variety of samples in similar and different contexts.

Finally, we were able to gain access to collect first-hand primary survey data to investigate connections between phenomena we hypothesised unlike relying on secondary survey data sources. Further, one of the firms in our sample provided unique set of data over seven months' period. Future research could be designed as longitudinal studies to further probe these relationships over time to gain a deeper understanding. Furthermore, our study was confined to the manufacturing plant of a firm. Therefore, future research could incorporate other practices related to backward and forward functions of value chain that are linked with lean production, manufacturing plant and firm performance of the firms.

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Figures

Figure 1. Effect of lean duration together with waste minimization, continuous improvement, defects minimization and JIT and pull on manufacturing performance

Figure 2. Effect of lean duration together with cross functional teams, employee involvement and information availability on manufacturing performance

Figure 3. Lean production practices over seven months

Figure 4. Manufacturing performance over seven months

Tables

Table 1. Commonly cited determinants of lean production

Study	Practices included	Method used to derive practices
James-Moore and Gibbons (1997)	Waste elimination, flexibility, people utilization, process control, and optimization	Scoring method
Koufteros et al. (1998)*	Shop-floor employee involvement in problem solving, re-engineering set-up, cellular manufacturing, quality improvement efforts, preventive maintenance, dependable suppliers, and pull production	Principle component factor analysis
Panizzolo (1998)	Process and equipment, manufacturing planning and control, human resources, product design, supplier relationships, and customer relationships	Principle component factor analysis
Flynn et al. (1999)**	Employee development, management technical competence, design for customer needs, worker participation, proprietary equipment, continuous improvement, process control, feedback of information, pull system, and JIT supplier relationship	Cronbach's alpha and inter-item correlation
Karlsson and Åhlström (1996)	Elimination of waste, continuous improvement, zero defects, JIT deliveries, pull of materials, multifunctional teams, decentralisation, integration of functions, and vertical information systems	Clinical research project
Shah and Ward (2003)	JIT, TQM, TPM, and HRM	Principle component factor analysis
Doolen and Hacker (2005)	Manufacturing equipment and processes, shop-floor management, new product development, supplier management, customer relationships, and workforce management	Conceptual
Shah and Ward (2007)	Supplier feedback, JIT delivery by suppliers, customer involvement, pull, continuous flow, set-up time reduction, TPM, statistical process control, and employee involvement	Principle component factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis
Dal Pont et al. (2008)	JIT, TQM, and HRM	Confirmatory factor analysis
Furlan et al. (2011)	JIT and TQM	Confirmatory factor analysis

Note: The table was created by the authors. * practices for time compression, ** practices for competitive performance

Table 2. Lean production practices

Item measure	Waste minimization	Defects minimization	Cross functional teams	Continuous improvement	JIT and pull	Information availability	Employee involvement
Lot sizes are maintained at the minimum possible level	.784						
Machine set-up times are maintained at the minimum possible level	.777						
Machine down time is maintained at the minimum possible level	.775						
Value of rework in relation to export orders is maintained at the minimum possible level	.769						
Value of waste in relation to export orders is maintained at the minimum possible level	.748						
Value of work in progress is maintained at the minimum possible level	.746						
Problems leading to defects are identified promptly to prevent occurrences of defects in the production line		.878					
Sources of defects are identified promptly through constant monitoring of production process		.859					
Defective parts (machine error) are identified promptly to take corrective action		.803					
Employees concern to manufacture fault free items		.769					
Rework area is maintained at the minimum possible level		.768					
Defective items (human error) are identified promptly to take corrective action		.763					
Performance of teams are being assessed using multiple criteria (such as quality and lead times)			.811				
Employees are given training on different functional areas (such as maintenance and quality control)			.796				
Employees are provided with leadership training for effective team working			.796				
Employees are given training on different tasks			.784				
Sufficient amount of training is given to newly hired employees to orient them to cross functional team work			.745				
Each employee rotates across different tasks in the shop-floor			.713				
Suggestions provided by employees had been implemented promptly				.857			
Employees actively involved in providing suggestions for continuous improvement				.816			
On the spot problem solving is in operation in an effective manner				.712			
Quality teams are operating in an effective manner				.710			

A formal employee suggestion scheme is operating in an effective manner						.701						
Amount of materials scheduled through backward requests is maintained at the maximum possible level						.801						
Usage of backward requests in the material flow is maintained at the maximum possible level						.783						
Amount of time spent in processing each order is maintained at the minimum possible level						.742						
Employees are provided with right parts, in the right quantity at the right point in time						.716						
Regular meetings are held to discuss information of the shop-floor with employees									.758			
Employees are provided with relevant information of the shop-floor regularly									.743			
Employees are provided with information of strategic nature (such as short and long term goals of the firm) constantly									.738			
Employees are provided with information about performance of different functional areas of the shop-floor									.732			
Employees are provided with relevant information of the shop-floor on time									.721			
Employees accept responsibility for their work in the shop-floor									.788			
Teams are assigned to perform supervisory tasks									.781			
Work content of teams have been broadened									.757			
Employees rotate team leadership among members in the team									.747			
Employees accept responsibility to perform tasks that span across different functional areas (such as maintenance and quality control)									.746			
Levels in the organization structure of the shop-floor is maintained at the minimum possible level									.717			
Cronbach's alpha						.83	.89	.84	.87	.84	.86	.88
AVE						.59	.65	.60	.58	.58	.55	.59
Construct reliability						.90	.92	.90	.87	.85	.86	.89

Table 3. Manufacturing performance

Item measure	Loading
Floor space saving (m ²)	.789
Delivery in full on time (DIFOT) (%)	.774
Efficiency of the process (%)	.767
Raw material on time delivery (%)	.735
Efficiency of machine operators (%)	.726
First time through (FIT) inspection (%)	.721
Accepted quality level (AQL) (%) at the end of the line	.714
Cronbach's alpha	.79
AVE	.56
Construct reliability	.90

Table 4. Construct correlation matrix

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Waste minimization	3.71	.67	.77								
2 Continuous improvement	3.57	.69	.712**	.76							
3 Defects minimization	3.68	.61	.666**	.698**	.81						
4 JIT and pull	3.75	.64	.711**	.715**	.722**	.76					
5 Cross functional teams	3.46	.72	.580**	.648**	.558**	.669**	.77				
6 Employee involvement	3.53	.66	.626**	.658**	.599**	.660**	.710**	.77			
7 Information availability	3.76	.52	.595**	.687**	.652**	.671**	.656**	.622**	.74		
8 Lean duration (yrs)	4.87	1.37	.475**	.453**	.539**	.564**	.469**	.503**	.426**	-	
9 Manufacturing performance	3.60	.58	.310**	.361**	.361**	.343**	.383**	.395**	.395**	.408**	.75

Notes: ** p < 0.01; diagonal entries, square root of AVE; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs

Table 5. Hierarchical regression analysis

	Model 1 B	Model 2 B	Model 3 B
<i>Step 1: Independent</i>			
Lean production practices:			
Waste minimization	.357***	.360***	.354***
Continuous improvement	.282***	.287***	.293***
Defects minimization	.219**	.221**	.224**
JIT and pull	.291***	.310***	.318***
Cross functional teams	.360***	.368***	.352***
Employee involvement	.387***	.389***	.372***
Information availability	.242**	.247**	.237**
<i>Step 2: Moderator</i>			
Lean duration		.274***	.397***
<i>Step 3: Interaction term</i>			
Waste minimization x Lean duration			.140**
Continuous improvement x Lean duration			.109**
Defects minimization x Lean duration			.123**
JIT and pull x Lean duration			.153**
Cross functional teams x Lean duration			.254***
Employee involvement x Lean duration			.232***
Information availability x Lean duration			.141**
R ²	.339***	.406***	.431***
R ² (Adj.)	.375***	.379***	.382***

Note: ** p<.01; *** p<.001; Standard errors for the variables were less than .45; Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; Bootstrap sample size = 5,000.